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Complete response after chemotherapy in HER2+ or triple negative breast cancer: surgery, radiotherapy or both?

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Neoadjuvant chemotherapy (NACT) is commonly used to treat patients with locally advanced (LABC) breast cancer. Pathologic complete response (pCR) to NACT improve disease free survival (DFS) and potentially overall survival (OS). Recent studies have shown that patients with triple negative breast cancer (TNBC) and HER2 + disease had higher pCR rates than patients with other breast cancer subtypes. However, data regarding the impact of adjuvant surgery, radiotherapy (RT) or both after NACT on locoregional relapse and patterns of failure are limited.

Downstaging allows performing breast conservative surgery in LABC patients. In TNBC the difference in DFS is not significantly associated with the type of surgery received. Some series have suggested expanding the role of postmastectomy RT to include patients with T1-2N0 breast cancer with high risk features like TNBC and HER2+. Also there are data to suggest high rates of local recurrence rate (LRR) despite the achievement of pCR in this subsets of patients. HER2 positivity do not appear to be associated with increased risk of LRR but triple negative status, however, does appear to increase the risk of LRR. This risk is high even if adjuvant radiation therapy is given. If there is nodal invasion, large residual tumor (ypT2), young patient age, lymphovascular invasion and high histological grade, RT shouldn't be omitted.

Decision for postmastectomy RT after NACT in TNBC and HER2+ patients should rely on several pre and post therapeutic factors, individual patient and tumor factors. If pCR is not obtained, further chemotherapy treatment intensification is recommended either by itself or combined with RT.

Key words: neoadjuvant chemotherapy, complete response, breast cancer